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Source: H.K.J. Cowan : Grammar of the Sentani Language,
'S-Gravenhage – Martinus Nijhoff, 1965

Phonology.

- // not word initial nor after C (allophone [d]), occurs only intervocalically
 - o exception word-initial // in the postposition *le~de* 'with, and', but this is an enclitic to the preceding word, so it is not a real exception – *le* occurs only after a vowel ending in a vowel, while *de* occurs only after words ending in a consonant
- verbal structure:
 - o verbal roots with more than one syllable ending in -ə preceded by one of the consonants allowed as finals tend to be treated as if they really end not in -ə but in this C
 - o bound allomorphs of such roots occurring in positions where a syllable closed by a C is no objection
 - o no roots end in the high vowels /i/ or /u/
- phonological processes:
 - o s-allophon of phonem /h/ - obligatory after nasals, /j/, /i/; optional after /w/
 - o after /j/, /w/ - [s], [f] as allophones of phonem /d/
 - o sometimes a neutralization between /d/ and // in intervocalic position; ex.: *ambulo* 'dead (man's) body' for **ambu-do*, from *do* 'man'
 - o nasalization of vowels when followed by syllable final nasal, often before [k], sometimes the nasal is dropped and the vowel slightly lengthened
 - o /h/ - allophones [s] restricted to and, except after /w/, obligatory in the position following /i/ or one of the only admissible syllable- and word closing consonants
 - o neutralisation of nasals in final position:
 - realized according to the following consonant in the word or phrase sandhi
 - but in pausal or non-assimilating position, e.g. before a vowel of a following word or in slow speech [m] is preferred in final position
 - ex.: *əmfɛ* 'banana leaf', *ənnɔ* 'banana tree trunk'
- Syllable:
 - o Consists of either one single vowel or such a vowel preceded or / and followed by one single C
 - o Nasals, semivowels are the only admitted syllable finals
 - o Initial syllable *wə-* in polysyllables frequently contracts to *u-*, *uw-*
- Word contains one or more such syllables, but it cannot consist of two or more vowels alone
 - o Structures of words: V, CV, VC, CVC, VCV, CVCV, VCVC, CVCVC, VCCV, CVCCV, CVCCVC, VCVCCV

- stress:

- in words of more than one syllable, stress lies on the syllabic preceding the last C of the word;
ex.: *'joku* 'dog', *ho'kolo* 'young'
- in words of three and four syllables, ending in a vowel, which have the antepenult closed by a C, the stress tends to shift to this syllable, if the penult is an open syllable in -ə;
ex.: *'wənəle* 'thou wilt say to him', *u'kajnəle* 'they told him'
- in longer words the main stress falls on the regular syllabic according to the basic rule, a secondary stress affecting the 3rd syllable forward from the main stress, or the 2nd syllable forward if this is closed by a C;
ex.: *ha,həwdo'koke* 'he hit me'; *ədəka'wale* 'I saw thee'
- many adverbs seems to have irregular stress, notably final even when the words end in a vowel
- negative prefix -ə + verb root beginning in ə : prefix is either added by means of the junction consonant -j- or it contracts with the ə of the root which is then somewhat lengthened and takes the stress – the relevant element is this stress and not the length; ex.: *ə-j-ə/ə-j*, but also *'ə/ə-j* 'not speak' as opposed to *ə'ləj* 'speak thou'
- verbal roots of more than one syllable ending in -ə preceded by one of the Cs admissible as finals tend to treat this C as root final and drop the -ə when an affix, beginning with aC follows
 - stress remains on the syllable which carries it in the root; ex.: *anə* 'eat': *'an(ə)ke* 'he ate', *'an(ə)ma* > *amma* 'let us eat'
 - but the stress shifts from this root syllable to affix (or one of them) in regular conformity with the basic rule, if it ends in a C itself; ex.: *a'nəj* 'eat!'
- in some adjectives and adverbs stress is found on the final syllable, when if this ends in a vowel, but it is doubtful whether this can be said to be a characteristic feature for these word classes;
ex.: *hə'lɛ-hə'lɛ* 'thin', *fə'nɛ* 'slippery'
- sometimes stress has distinctive function, but often irregularities have no distinctive function;
ex.: *'kala* 'shellfish' vs. *ka'la* 'shout, yell' – irregular stress placement

- reduplication:

- forms a verbal noun or gerund
- derivational
- characteristic of a single unit both in stress and meaning
- usually adjectives and adverbs
- whole root reduplicated, if it ends in [ŋ], it changes to [m];
ex.: *kələn-kələm* 'dry', *hələ-hələ* 'thin', *dun-dum* 'fat'
- a variant of this type is repetition with vowel or even syllable variation (apophony) in the 2nd constituent;
ex.: *dəwbəhi-dawbəhi* 'here and there, hither and tither',
ədəj-mədəj 'invisible, unseen'

- structurally two types:
 - a disyllabic or polysyllabic root ending in -ə preceded by one of the consonants admitted as finals: tend to treat this C as final – repeats the root in this form with the C as final; ex.: *dow-dow* from *dowə* ‘take’
 - all other roots
- may enter in composite verbal forms
- repetition of verbal forms: syntactical coordinative construction because the constituents are each fully, independently and identically inflected forms, retaining their proper stress and the meaning
 - ex.: *awkəjde awkəjde* ‘they rowed and rowed’
 - combination of the gerund with an other form of the same root as derivational composition with possible variation; ex.: *hikoj-sakoj* ‘exhausted’; *ədəj-mədəj* ‘invisible’
- compositional forms distinguish between morphology and syntax:
 - usually two constituent words which together have the characteristics of a single unit
 - sometimes the compound consists of a short phrase in which case it may contain more than two constituents
 - ex.: *do – mije* ‘human being(s)’, from *do* ‘man’ and *mije* ‘woman’
isam - fə’la ‘war’, from *isam* ‘anger’ and *fə’la* ‘bow-and-arrow’
 - a sort of abstract nouns is sometimes indicated by preposing the 3rd person pronoun *n-*, *na-*, *nə-* in composition; ex.: *na-hələ* ‘justice’ from *hələ* ‘right, true, real’
- composite verbal forms:
 - composed of two differently inflected roots, the first of which indicates a movement, are found in various combinations:
 - both in present
 - both in habitualis, second being either a primary (without aspectual affixes) or secondary (with aspectual affixes)
 - first in imperfect, second in aorist and either primary or secondary
 - first in aorist, second present
 - first in aorist, second imperfect
 - first in aorist, second in the aorist of secondary form with directive aspect suffix
 - both in future, second either primary or secondary
 - first in adhortative, second either in simple-root form or in secondary form
 - structurally two principal categories can be distinguished:
 - first verb is in an imperfective or undeterminate form, followed by the second verb in a perfective or determinate form, except the secondary habitualis or iterative of type 2, which follows category two
category one comprises types 3, 7, 8
 - all other combinations except types 7, 8, which follows category one
category two comprises all other types

- characteristic differences in structures between category one and two:
 - in II the 2nd constituent is fully inflected according to mood, tense and person for the subject concerned as primary or secondary form; the only flexional affixes occurring on the 1st constituent are those for tense and person for the subject (some exceptions p. 36)
 - in I the 2nd constituent has exactly the same flexional affixes as those following the aspect affix in non-composite secondary forms of the corresponding tenses and moods; flexional elements in the 1st constituent are also in accordance with those which, in the corresponding tenses and moods of non-composite secondary forms, follow the root and precede the aspect affix (exceptions p. 36)
- morphophonemic rule: if the 2nd constituent begins with a vowel and the preceding flexional element of the 1st constituent ends in a vowel, the two vowels are not contracted or assimilated, but linked by –j– ; ex.: *ma-j-anə-n-ko-n-de* ‘we two shall come-eat’ (1.dual.fut. of *mə-*, ‘come’, plus *anə-* with asp.aff. –*ko*, ‘eat’; type 7)
- combination of gerund with other forms of the same root as flexional composition, not even as flexional repetition :
 - although the two constituents contain the same root, with the same meaning, they are formally and functionally different
 - unlike syntactical repetition of verbal forms the two constituents are not identical and not independent, do not have each the same functional position in the compound

Morphology and Syntax

- morphological structure of a word:
 - word – either a single or a complex form, but a form is not necessarily a word, because some forms occur in bound position only
 - simple word contains one root
 - complex word consists of one or more root to which a morphological process has been applied like: prefixation of verbal root of negative prefix *ə-*, affixation (elements follow roots irrespective of their own mutual order), phonetic root change or apophony, suppletion, repetition, composition, combination of two or more of these processes
- verbal structure:
 - consists of one or two verbal roots (the same or different) + suffixes (the only prefix is the negation)
 - frequent contraction of affixes
- modal sign is the final element in the verbal structure:
 - follow in general the person subject affix and coincides with it in some cases (p. 21)
 - in composed verbal forms the second constituent of the compound

carries the indicative sign and this follows either the same rules as for the present, the habitualis or the imperfect on the one hand, or those for the secondary aorist or the secondary future on the other according whether the compound is one of the first or second category (look section verb compound)

- aspect: if aspect affix begins with a vowel and the preceding flexional element of the verb ends in a vowel, the two vowels are not contracted, but linked by the consonant *-j-*
- person affixes:
 - o initial *ə* drop after preceding vowel, while initial *a* persists after preceding *a*, *ə* or back vowel and contract to *ɛ* with a preceding front vowel
- particle:
 - o vetative formed by prefixing *ə-* or *ə-j-* in combination with an enclitic particle *jɛ* following the person affix and assimilating to it retrogressively to *-mɛ* after the *m* of the person marker
 - o emphatic particle *jɛ* helps to form predicative constructions consisting of a subject only
- postpositional phrase:
 - o consists of a noun, pronoun or verbal form followed by a postposition or, except with verbal forms, a postpositional phrase as relation marker
 - o postposition is enclitic, ex.: *ifa na* 'in the (men's) canoe', *bu nə* 'in the water'
 - o if a noun is followed by an adjective, the postposition follows the latter
 - o in construction consisting of a noun or pronoun followed by a postpositional phrase, the latter functions as a pseudo postposition itself; ex.: *bu əj nə* 'in the water' i.e. 'mid lake' (lit.: in the water's inside)
 - o postpositional phrase may be stressed as such by the emphatic particle *jɛ*
 - o can also be repeated; ex.: *nɛj də nɛj də danojkoke* 'they both pulled (it) to themselves, i.e. each to himself'
- sentence can be at the same time a phrase and a word;
ex.: *hədəke* 'he (has) died'
- phrase sandhi:
 - o strong tendency for phrase sandhi whence both morphological and syntactical constructions are close units, phonetically, while both stress and meaning are not always decisive
 - o not in every case clear marked as one unit
 - o ex.: *jej bi foma do də mijɛ də jejbojmɛ də bodojdobojmɛ*
'hey there, coconut rat, if you could become a human being, you would understand me' the two constituents of what should be the one composite word *do-mijɛ* are each separately followed by the postposition *də*
 - o sometimes stress seems to be more distinctive;
ex.: *kaji-i'fa: kaji* und *i'fa* carry both an irregular final stress, the two vowels never seem to be contracted as in other cases

